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PROTECTING AND RESTORING BIODIVERSITY USING MAINSTREAM FINANCE

D3.2: Policy Brief: Classifying Ecosystem and Biodiversity Values for Better Policy and Finance Decisions

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Funded by
the European Union

Grant Agreement No.	101135476
Project Acronym	BIOFIN-EU
Project Title	Protecting and Restoring Biodiversity using Mainstream Finance
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA
Horizon Europe Call Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-9
Start – ending date	1 January 2024 - 31 December 2026
Project Website	biofin-project.eu
Work Package	WP3: Economic Valuation of Ecosystem Services
WP Lead Beneficiary	University of Gothenburg
Relevant Task(s)	T3.1 NBS Governance Structures and Ecosystem Services Valuation. T3.2 Valuation of ecosystem services and corporate finance decision-making
Deliverable type Dissemination level	R – Report PU: Public
Due Date of Deliverable	30 June 2025
Actual Submission Date	13 June 2025
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Recommended citation

BIOFIN-EU; Fredrik Carlsson, Mitesh Kataria, Elina Lampi (2025), Policy Brief: Classifying ecosystem and biodiversity values for better policy and finance decisions. BIOFIN-EU, Deliverable 3.2, interim report, pp. 1-10

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Executive Summary

Nature is essential for economic development and human well-being. Yet, biodiversity and ecosystem services continue to decline at alarming rates, driven by a mismatch between ecological values and financial and policy incentives. A central challenge in addressing this crisis is to avoid undervaluation of biodiversity, particularly the non-market benefits provided by ecosystems.

This brief presents a framework for classifying the value of biodiversity and ecosystem services and linking these values to policy, planning, and finance. It describes multiple types of values—direct use, indirect use, non-use, and option values—and outlines appropriate economic valuation methods for each, focusing on the human values arising from biodiversity and ecosystems. Furthermore, it provides a structured typology for Nature-based Solutions (NbS), enabling alignment of ecological interventions with policy priorities and financial tools. Together, value classification and NbS typologies form the foundation for well-informed and equitable investment in biodiversity, guiding us to achieve long-term sustainability goals.

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1. Why valuing nature matters

Biodiversity is the variability of living organisms across terrestrial, marine, and freshwater ecosystems. It is not only a matter of conservation, but the basis for ecosystem services that humans rely on every day: clean air and water, pollination, flood protection, disease regulation, and cultural identity. Many of these services ecosystems provide are classic public goods—non-rivalrous and non-excludable. Thus, although ecosystem services have economic value, most of these services are neither correctly allocated nor priced by markets. This creates a market failure, where private incentives to conserve biodiversity are insufficient, and the social value of ecosystems goes unrecognized.

The lack of formal markets makes it difficult to account for ecosystems and biodiversity in cost-benefit analyses or financial decision-making. This underpins chronic underinvestment in them and limits the scale and ambition of NbS, i.e., ecosystem-based interventions designed to address societal challenges. As a result, ecosystems are degraded or lost because their societal benefits do not show up on balance sheets or in public budgets.

Given these unpriced societal values, markets alone cannot accurately capture the full scope and worth of biodiversity, underscoring the need for policies to correct this market failure. Policies can set the agenda for what needs to be achieved, such as the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (European Commission, 2020) and the Water Framework Directive (European Commission, Directive 2000/60/EC). Thus, effective environmental regulation, green finance frameworks, and biodiversity incentives require a clear understanding of all the types and magnitudes of ecosystem values. A robust classification of these values and the development of tools to assess them is therefore a necessary foundation for a nature-positive economy.

2. Understanding different ecosystem values

Ecosystems primarily benefit people through so-called ecosystem services. The Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) defines three broad categories of ecosystem services:

- **Provisioning services:** Food, fibre, raw materials, water, and genetic resources from flora and fauna.
- **Regulating and maintenance services:** Pollination, pest control, climate regulation, carbon sequestration, water regulation and purification, and flood prevention.
- **Cultural services:** Spiritual experiences, aesthetic appreciation, habitat for wildlife conservation, and spaces for recreational activities.

The total value of ecosystem services consists of use values, non-use values, and option values.

2.1. Use Values

Use values are benefits derived from direct or indirect interaction with ecosystems. They include:

- **Direct use values:** Tangible goods used directly, such as food, timber, and recreational opportunities. Since actors have an interest in protecting ecosystems and making sure that they provide necessary services for the production and consumption of various goods, these values are often partially reflected in markets.
- **Indirect use values:** Services that support life or production indirectly, such as climate regulation, water purification, or soil stabilization. These are less likely to be priced in markets but are essential for long-term human well-being.

2.2. Non-Use Values

Non-use values reflect the value people assign to nature independent of any current or planned own use. These include:

- **Existence value:** The value of knowing biodiversity or ecosystem services exist.
- **Bequest value:** The value of preserving biodiversity and ecosystem services for future generations.
- **Altruistic value:** The value of others in society being able to enjoy biodiversity and ecosystem services.

Since non-use values often make up a large part of the total value of an ecosystem, they are particularly important in biodiversity policy. These values reflect ethical, cultural, and moral motivations for conservation. However, because they are not associated with market transactions, assigning a value for them requires specialized economic valuation methods.

2.3. Option Values

Option values represent the value of keeping ecosystems intact for possible future uses, some of which may not yet be known. This is particularly relevant under uncertainty. The precautionary principle and the risk of irreversible damage, as e.g. biodiversity loss, make option values especially important for decision-making.

3. Classifying Nature-based Solutions

Nature-based Solutions (NbS) are ecosystem-based interventions making use of natural capital and designed to address societal challenges, such as climate change, water management, and problems of urbanization, while providing co-benefits for biodiversity, habitat, and human well-being. Examples include:

- Restoring wetlands for flood control and habitat.
- Providing urban green spaces for cooling, recreation, and health.
- Forest and peatland conservation to store carbon and preserve species.
- Restoring the marine environment to increase fish stock and prevent biodiversity loss.

NbS are increasingly seen as essential for addressing climate change, reducing disaster risk, and improving public health. But to scale up NbS investment, policymakers and financiers need a shared language to describe and evaluate and value them. However, the variety of forms that NbSs take makes it difficult to standardize assessments or determine their value. We therefore propose a structure typology for NbS:

- **Type of intervention:** From conservation of natural ecosystems (low intervention) to creation of new ecosystems (high intervention).
- **Environment type:** Urban, coastal, forest, wetland, agricultural, marine etc.
- **Societal challenge addressed:** Climate and flood resilience, water security, food security (pollination and soil conservation), physical and mental health benefits, disaster risk reduction, mitigating pollution, etc.
- **Approach used:** Restoration, preservation, ecological engineering, green infrastructure, etc.

This classification supports planning, monitoring, and financing of NbS. It also helps in designing appropriate indicators and matching solutions to local needs.

It is also worth mentioning that NbS relies on natural capital to protect and restore biodiversity but can of course involve man-made capital as well. However, nature-positive investments that rely solely on natural capital would not be seen as an NbS, such as investments in capital to reduce biodiversity loss from wastewater.

4. Methods for valuing ecosystem services

For goods/values where sufficiently well-functioning markets exist, market behaviour gives information on the size of the values of the ecosystems. For non-market values, economists have developed non-market valuation methods to provide estimates that can be used in a normative decision-making framework, such as cost-benefit analysis (CBA), to guide the decision on the appropriate investment level in biodiversity. Economic valuation methods can be grouped into three main families: revealed preferences, stated preferences, and production-based approaches.

4.1. Revealed preference methods

These methods infer value for a public (often environmental) good from observed behaviour in existing markets for a related private good:

- **Travel Cost Method:** Measures the value of recreational sites by observing how much money and time people spend visiting them.
- **Hedonic Pricing Method:** Infers environmental values from property prices, for example, the premium paid for cleaner air, less noise, or proximity to green space. Although these environmental attributes are not directly traded in markets, they are embedded in various characteristics of a property and are thus reflected in its market value.

These methods capture only the use values and rely on the existence of complementary markets.

4.2. Stated preference methods

Stated preference methods rely on surveys or interviews to elicit individuals' willingness to pay for public (often environmental) goods. These methods are based on hypothetical scenarios, since no actual money transactions take place. They can be used to estimate the values of goods that do not have a market or a change in the quality of an existing good. Since it is possible to send a survey to a random sample of the population, and not only to ask those who are users of the good, stated preference methods are, therefore the only techniques capable of capturing non-use values.

- **Contingent Valuation:** Asks directly how much people would pay for e.g. specific conservation outcomes.
- **Choice Experiments:** Present respondents with choices between different scenarios with varying attributes that describe a public good. From their choices, it is possible to estimate in monetary terms how much or little respondents value each of the attributes.

4.3. Production function approaches

These estimates show how ecosystem services contribute to the production of market goods. For example, assessing the role of pollination in agricultural yields or the role of wetlands in flood protection. These methods help link ecosystem health to economic performance.

5. Challenges in valuation

While economic valuation is a powerful tool, it faces several challenges:

- **Non-market values** are often poorly understood or ignored in decision-making. Non-use values are essential for valuing biodiversity as well as planning biodiversity policies, especially when evaluating projects with few direct market links. Stated preference methods are the only methods that can measure non-use values.
- **Uncertainty and irreversibility** complicate valuation. Option values must be accounted for under risk.
- **Complexity and uninformed citizens:** Biodiversity is complex. It is therefore not very realistic that actors are fully informed when making decisions that can affect biodiversity.
- **Time horizons:** Ecosystems provide long-term benefits, while markets and policies often prioritize short-term gains. Moreover, since ecosystems provide benefits in the future, discounting must be taken into account.
- **Equity and distribution:** Values differ across populations. Valuation must consider who benefits, and who bears the costs.

Addressing these challenges requires thoughtful application of valuation methods, clear communication, and integration into planning and policy instruments.

6. From Classification to Action

Value classification and NbS typologies provide a practical foundation for embedding biodiversity in policy and finance.

Policy and Regulation

Governments can integrate ecosystem values into Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs), Strategic Environmental Assessments (SEAs), and natural capital accounting. Classification helps standardize evaluation and ensures consistency across sectors.

Strategic Planning and Investment

Understanding the full value of ecosystem services and biodiversity supports better decisions in, among others, land use, infrastructure, and public health. Cost-benefit analyses that include non-use values of ecosystem services and biodiversity are more likely to favour NbS over traditional grey infrastructure.

Public Finance

Valuation helps justify public and private investment in biodiversity and to design subsidies or taxes to implement this. For example, payment for ecosystem services (PES) schemes can be targeted to areas with high indirect-use or non-use values. Taxes can be imposed on activities damaging biodiversity, such as pollution discharges.

Private Investment

Clear classification supports the development of biodiversity credits, green bonds, and risk assessment frameworks. Financial actors need valuation data to assess returns and align with sustainability standards.

Equity and Participation

Valuation frameworks should reflect diverse perspectives. Recognizing non-use values such as existence and bequest values ensures future generations and marginalized voices are considered. Participatory valuation can support more inclusive and legitimate decisions.

Nature Positive Investments

It is important to consider how NbS fit into the broader scheme of nature positive investments, and in particular how nature-based solutions can be combined with investments in man-made capital such as infrastructure.

7. Recommendations for Policymakers

1. **Recognize all ecosystem values in planning and policy.** Use a comprehensive classification of use, non-use, and option values.
2. **Adopt standardized NbS typologies.** Facilitate comparison, reporting, and monitoring across programs.
3. **Integrate valuation at all levels of governance.** From urban planning to national accounting.
4. **Promote capacity building.** Train public officials and stakeholders to use and interpret valuation tools and data.
5. **Use valuation to mobilize finance.** Link ecosystem services and biodiversity values to public and private finance mechanisms.
6. **Ensure equity and inclusiveness.** Incorporate non-market, intergenerational, and ethical values in decision-making.

8. Conclusion

To halt and reverse biodiversity loss and to deliver climate and development goals, societies must recognize and act upon the full value of nature. A classification of all types of ecosystem values and NbS typologies offers a concrete well-established and practical way to do this. By embedding these frameworks into policy, finance, and planning, we can ensure smarter investments, more resilient communities, and a thriving natural world for generations to come.